

LSRS Conference: Future of european law & society

09:00-10:00 Coffee Moment and Welcoming guests

10:00-10:30 Official Welcome LSRS (Otilia Apostol), Institutional greetings (Alin Mituță),
Introducing the Conference (Simona Fabiola Gîrneată)

10:30-12:00 First Panel - Citizenship Unveiled: Exploring the Legal Challenges in European Society

Moderator: Vlad Bărbat

Speakers: Valeriu Ciucă; Felix Hodoș; Luca Brocca

12:00 - 13:00 Lunch Break

13:00 - 14:30 Second Panel - Governance Beyond Borders: Shaping the Future of European Politics

Moderator: Sabina Grigore

Speakers: Marcu Solomon; Simion Costea; Simina Tulbure; Codrin Codrea

14:30 - 15:00 Coffee Break

15:00 - 16:30 Third Panel - Current Challenges: Addressing Cyber Disruptions and Technological Advancements

Moderator: Ștefan Vișinescu

Speakers: Răzvan Ceuca; Sebastian-Dan Naste, Catherine De Weever, Andrada

Balmez

16:30 - 17:00 Conclusions of the Conference